

Forms of Organizing Medical and Pedagogical Control of Student Athletes

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Abstract:

It is a special branch of medical science and practice, which is responsible for the medical and biological maintenance of the preparation of athletes - in general, it is an integral part of sports training designed to solve a number of specific tasks. Organizations engaged in medical control of athletes' training are united under the auspices of the International Federation of Sports Medicine.

Keywords: In sports, medical supervision, pedagogical supervision, medical supervision, biological support, operational examination, training.

INTRODUCTION

The science of sports medicine is a special branch of clinical medicine. This science determines the health, physical development, training and functional capabilities of various tissue-organ systems of those engaged in physical education and sports training through medical supervision. In addition, he deals with the issues of determining the causes of diseases and injuries that may occur in athletes, their prevention, treatment, and restoration of the athlete's strength.

This discipline, as a companion to the special disciplines of physical culture, advises the teacher-trainer on the need to pay special attention to the health and fitness level of the exerciser when determining the size and speed of exercise. Thus, the science of sports medicine is an integral part of physical culture and sports sciences and is directly related to the training of a physical education teacher and sports trainer as a specialist.

In the process of preparation of this teaching-methodical guide, information published in various literary and informational sources, including on Internet sites, was used. The obtained data were compared with each other, and the confirmed data were compiled. Since the literary data were mainly published in Russian and other foreign languages, they were translated into Uzbek using Uzbek-Russian medical dictionaries.

The collected information was formalized in the recommended sequence based on the requirements for textbooks.

Expected results - in the current period, when the program of training highly educated personnel, including physical education and sports specialists, is changing, and training of high-class and qualified specialists is required in the Republic of Uzbekistan, this educational-methodological manual will be useful. It can be hoped that it will. In the process of being useful, the following can be achieved: prevention of various diseases and injuries; make a correct and reasonable diagnosis; correct and uncomplicated treatment; improvement of rehabilitation, etc.

MAIN PART.

Medical-pedagogical supervision is defined as examinations conducted by a doctor and a coach during training, physical education classes or during competitions. With the help of such control, the effect of physical exercises on the body of those engaged in physical education and sports is assessed, the level of functional physical fitness of the body is determined, and the training process is improved based on these checks.

In the medical-pedagogical control, operative (in a short period of time), daily and every-stage inspections are carried out, which are part of the structure of the medical biological support of the training of athletes.

Short-term training effect is evaluated in operative tests. The following forms of medical-pedagogical control are used during operative examinations:

- a) inspections conducted during the entire training, in each part of the training;
- b) inspections conducted before training and 20-30 minutes after training;
- c) morning and evening on the training day.

During the training, the checks conducted after each part of the training are carried out only if the trainer is interested in the correct structure of the training. If medical-pedagogical control is organized in such a form, certain indicators are checked before training, after each part of training, after performing an exercise, after rest and after training. It should be said that the medical-pedagogical supervision during the entire training requires a lot of work and to some extent interferes with the training process. Therefore, this form of medical-pedagogical control is used in cases where it is very necessary. By comparing the indicators of the functional state of the participants before and after the training, it is possible to assess the amount of loading and the level of preparation of the athlete. In order to study the effect of the load on the body from one day's training, tests are carried out in the morning and in the evening.

In the daily tests, the training effect is evaluated after a certain period of time, that is, during the last phases of recovery. The form of organization of such inspections may be as follows:

- a) every morning before training;
- b) morning and evening for several days;
- c) at the beginning and at the end of one or two microcycles;
- d) one day after training, sometimes 1-2 days later.

In order to plan loads for the microcycle, determine the day of high-intensity training, and determine the level of recovery after various types of training, checks are carried out daily throughout the microcycle.

Inspections at each stage are of great importance for planning and personalizing the training process, as it evaluates the cumulative effect of training at a given stage. In this case, it is determined to what extent the task assigned to this stage has been completed.

It is necessary to compare the work done, the training methods and tools used with the changes that occurred during the entire stage, and draw the necessary conclusions for planning the next training process. The doctor's task in performing these tasks is to evaluate the general working ability of the organism, changes in its functional state. Psychological readiness should be assessed. The task of the coach is to evaluate the level of functional training of the athlete.

Inspections at each stage should be carried out once every 2-3 months. Checks should be done after a day of rest, 1-2 hours after breakfast. Before the tests, the athlete should not exercise.

The coach and the doctor, the athlete can get the information that is important for them by analyzing the indicators of self-examination. These data, combined with daily checks and various tests, help to evaluate the effectiveness of the training microcycle structure. Every athlete should keep a self-monitoring diary.

The diary should also contain information about mood, sleep, appetite, work ability. The diary should also include pulse and respiratory rate in 1 minute, vital capacity of the lungs, weight, arterial blood pressure and hand dynamometry. The following can also be written in the diary: deterioration of health, violation of work order, etc.

It is necessary to ask the employee how he feels before and during training, whether he is tired, whether he wants to work, or how difficult it is to perform certain exercises. Absence of complaints and feeling good does not always indicate that the body is well adapted to loads. Because in some diseases, for example, heart failure, it can be detected only with the help of special methods. If the exerciser has some complaints during the exercise and after the exercise, this indicates that the loads are not suitable for the exerciser's training and his health has deteriorated.

In conclusion, it can be said that in the organization of medical-pedagogical supervision of athletes, the doctor, coach and athlete should work together.

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